

Report on IReL workshop at CONUL conference 2024

Jack Hyland, IReL and Susan Reilly, IReL

© the authors, 2024. This work is openly licensed via CC BY 4.0.

At the CONUL conference in Belfast in June 2024, Susan Reilly and Jack Hyland from IReL led a workshop titled “OA in 2030: IReL planning for the growth of OA in Ireland”. The workshop was primarily attended by library staff of all grades, and also by publishers.

We introduced the workshop by presenting on the strategic background: Ireland’s commitment to “a sustainable and inclusive course for achieving 100% open access to research publications by 2030”; Ireland’s successes to date in the transition to open access and the role of IReL’s OA publishing agreement in this; and an overview of global trends in such agreements.

We showed that, measured by publications from corresponding authors affiliated with IReL member institutions, we have reached about 70% OA per year, but growth has slowed in recent years.

Figure 1. Percentage split of OA versus closed publications by IReL member affiliated corresponding authors, 2013-2023. Source: OpenAlex.

And hybrid open access publishing, largely driven by transformative agreements supported by IReL, has become the largest mode of open access:

Figure 2: Count of publications by IReL member affiliated corresponding authors, by OA type, 2017-2022. Source: OpenAlex.

IReL provides Irish researchers with a comprehensive suite of OA publishing options: in 2023, 79% of articles by corresponding authors affiliated with IReL member institutions were with the 24 publishers IReL has such agreements with (but noting that IReL-funded OA is not an option for every article). IReL’s OA publishing agreements also support publishing in fully OA (Gold) journals, but not as comprehensively as hybrid OA journals: in 2022, 12% of IReL funded articles were in fully OA journals.

A key motivation with transformative agreements has been that delivered at scale globally, they would allow a critical mass of scholarly publications to be OA, making the legacy subscription/closed access model redundant. However, in spite of new countries continuing to adopt TAs (notably South Africa and France recently), and a small number of publishers committing to reach 100% OA in the coming years (ACM, Royal Society, Royal Society of Chemistry, Cambridge University Press), there appears to be no immediate prospect of a mass global flip while countries such as China (the world’s largest creator of research publications) do not yet prioritise OA.

However, the NORF Action Plan states that paying to publish in “hybrid journals is not supported, except as a limited part of transformative agreements with a clearly defined timeframe”, so we accept that TAs should not be supported indefinitely. We asked delegates at the workshop to explore and discuss questions around the future directions of open access. Each table was given a series of topic cards and posed with questions such as:

- How can we reconcile IReL’s continued spending on closed access subscriptions with NORF’s 100% OA goal?
- How should we address the growth of “APCs in the wild” (per-article fees for OA articles outside of negotiated agreements)?
- How can we help to grow Diamond OA (OA without per-publication fees)?
- With limited resources, should our priority be either:
 - Global equity: ensuring there are no financial barriers to any authors?
 - Or meeting local needs: prioritising OA for our institutions’ authors?

In the limited time for our workshop (one hour), we didn’t expect delegates to reach solutions or consensus on such complex questions. Rather, we treated the workshop as a chapter in an ongoing dialogue within our community. We paraphrase below a selection of the sentiments from the delegates at the workshop:

- “Some of IReL’s OA publishing agreements are capped (ie offering only a fixed number of OA articles per year). It was widely agreed that this is very frustrating for authors, who have no way of knowing if their publication can be offered IReL-funded OA on acceptance.”
- “It’s challenging for libraries to move away from subscribing to closed content while there is still demand from our users for it”
- “Irish libraries do much to promote and facilitate OA, but we are limited if authors (Irish and internationally) ultimately don’t/can’t choose to make their work OA”
- “There is a pressing need to monitor Irish institutions and funders growing spend on APCs in the wild”
- “Diamond OA has an important role to play but there are challenges in achieving buy-in from researchers”
- “We need to continue this conversation!”

Appendix: topic cards from the workshop

1. The future of pay-to-read

Discussion prompt questions:

- How can we reconcile IReL's continued spending on **closed access subscriptions** with **NORF's 100% OA goal**?
- Should IReL proactively divest from subscribing to closed content, or wait-and-see how the global OA transition develops?
- What can IReL member libraries do to foster the transition away from closed access?

2. APCs in-the-wild

Discussion prompt questions:

- IReL member institutions manage payments of at least €2.1M per year on APCs in-the-wild with fully-OA publishers.
- What can/should IReL and member libraries do about this?
- If we take no action, will the volume of APCs paid rise or fall?
- How will the policies landscape affect this trend?
- Should libraries help manage APC payments?
- Should libraries monitor APC payments?

3. Diamond OA

Discussion prompt questions:

- Should resources be redirected from IReL's and/or its members' library budgets to support Diamond OA?
- How else could we help scale Diamond OA?
- With limited resources, how do we prioritise which Diamond OA initiatives to support?
- How can we incentivise authors to publish Diamond?

4. A pay-to-publish future

Discussion prompt questions:

- When we are paying for OA publishing, should our priority be either:
 - **Global equity:** ensuring there are no financial barriers to any authors?
 - Or meeting local needs: prioritising **OA for our institutions' authors**?
- If IReL or an institution is paying for OA on authors' behalf, how do we best balance **our responsibilities using public money** with the **authors' choice of where to publish**?
- Should high income countries pay more to publish, if it supports affordable OA publishing in low income countries ?